

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART I. N¹-THIOBIAZOLYL-SULPHANILAMIDES

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Some *N*-thiothiazolyl sulphonamide amides have been prepared with a view to testing their efficacy against bacterial infection.

Ever since the epoch-making discovery of the specific antistreptococcal action of Prontosil (hydrochloride of 4-sulphamido-2':4'-diaminoazobenzene) by Domagk (*Deut. Med. Wschr.*, 1935, 61 250; *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1935, 48, 657; *Klin. Wschr.*, 1936, 18, 1585) and of the simpler compound, sulphanilamide (*cf.* Trefouel *et al.*, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1935, 120, 756; *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1937, 58, 30; Fuller, *Lancet*, 1937, 1, 194), numerous compounds of this group have been prepared for testing their anti-bacterial property. It is, however, to be observed that out of these, only a few, *viz.*, sulphanilamide (I, R=H), sulphapyridine (II), sulphathiazole (III), sulphadiazine (IV) and sulphaguanidine (V), appear to find great favour in the treatment of the various bacterial infections at the present day.

A close study of sulphonamides, hitherto described in literature, reveals the very interesting fact that majority of them that are found promising, possesses characteristic heterocyclic residues at N¹ (for nomenclature, *vide*, Crossley *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2217) and in a search for better drugs during the past three years, sulphonamide derivatives of pyridine, thiazole, diazine, pyrazine, piperazine, pyrrole, thiophene, furane, acridine, quinoline, *isoquinoline*, carbazole, benzothiazole, etc., have been synthesised by various workers in the field and their pharmacological activity studied though without much success.

It has been the intention of the senior author (P.C.G.) ever since the inception of research on sulphonamides in this department, to study sulphanilamide derivatives possessing at N¹ various types of heterocyclic ring systems and open chain systems containing sulphur and nitrogen. The present paper forms the first part of a systema-

matic study of these compounds, and the preparation of sulphanilamide derivatives of 1:3:4-thiobiazole of the types (VI and VII) of 5-methyl-thiobiazole (VIII) and of 5-methyl-thiol-thiobiazole (IX) have been described. It may be observed in this connection that all

the compounds described in this paper contain the active grouping, $\text{RNH}'\text{C}(:\text{N})-\text{S}$ which is also present in the sulphathiazole molecule and it was thus expected that they would possess antibacterial properties.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2:5-Di(acetylsulphanilamido)-1:3:4-thiobiazole (VI, $\text{R} = \text{Ac}'\text{NH}'\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$).—A solution of 2:5-diamino-1:3:4-thiobiazole (5 g.), prepared according to Guha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1039), in acetone (40 c.c.) and pyridine (5 c.c.), was treated with crystallised *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphochloride (18 g.), and heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. The solid separating, on cooling the solution, was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 252-54°. (Found: N, 16'0; S, 18'2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$ requires N, 16'47; S, 18'82 per cent).

2:5-Di-(sulphanilamido)-1:3:4-thiobiazole (VI, $\text{R} = \text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$).—The above acetyl compound (5 g.) was refluxed with 3*N*-hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 3 hours. The hydrochloride obtained after evaporation of the product, gave on neutralisation with sodium carbonate, the free base which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 223°. (Found: N, 19'2; S, 21'8. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires N, 19'72; S, 22'53 per cent).

2-Sulphanilamido-1:3:4-thiobiazole (VII, $\text{R} = \text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$).—A solution of 2-amino-1:3:4-thiobiazole (5 g. Freund and Menicke, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 2514) in pyridine (25 c.c.) and acetone (10 c.c.) was treated with *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphochloride (11'5 g.) and heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. After keeping the product overnight and dilution with water, a high melting substance was obtained. (Found: N, 17'9; S, 20'9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$ requires N, 18'79; S, 21'47 per cent) which was directly hydrolysed by boiling with 3*N*-hydrochloric acid (35 c.c.) till a clear solution was produced (about 2 hours). After cooling and neutralising with sodium carbonate the sulphamido-thiobiazole separated. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 213-14°. (Found: N, 21'2; S, 24'7. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires N, 21'87; S, 25'0 per cent).

2-Acetylsulphanilamido-5-methyl-1:3:4-thiobiazole (VIII, $\text{R} = \text{Ac}'\text{NH}'\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$).—A solution of 2-amino-5-methyl-1:3:4-thiobiazole (5 g.) prepared according to the method of Freund and Menicke (*loc. cit.*) in pyridine (15 c.c.) and acetone (10 c.c.) was treated with *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (10 g.) and heated on the water-bath

for 2 hours. After keeping for 12 hours at room temperature the product, isolated in the usual way, crystallised from acetone, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found : N, 17'4 ; S, 20'0. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 17'95 ; S, 20'51 per cent).

2-Sulphanilamido-5-methyl-1:3:4-thiobiazole (VIII, $R=H_2N\cdot C_6H_4SO_2$).—The acetyl compound (5 g.) was boiled with 3*N*-hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 3 hours when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was filtered, neutralised with sodium carbonate and the precipitated solid crystallised successively from alcohol and acetone, m.p. 186° - 87° . (Found : N, 20'4 ; S, 23'2. $C_9H_{10}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 20'74 ; S, 23'7 per cent).

2-Acetylsulphanilamido-5-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiobiazole (IX, $R=AcHN\cdot C_6H_4SO_2$).—A solution of 2-amino-5-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiobiazole (5 g.), prepared essentially according to the method of Busch (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1916, *ii*, 93, 357), in alcohol (15 c.c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) was treated with *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride (8 g.) and heated on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The solid, that separated out on cooling, was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 216° - 13° . (Found : N, 15'9 ; S, 27'2. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 16'28 ; S, 27'9 per cent).

2-Sulphamido-5-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiobiazole (IX, $R=H_2N\cdot C_6H_4SO_2$).—The above acetyl compound (5 g.) was boiled with 3*N*-hydrochloric acid (28 c.c.) till a clear solution was obtained. After neutralisation of the product with sodium carbonate solution, the precipitated solid was collected and crystallised from hot alcohol, m.p. 198° . (Found : N, 18'2 ; S, 31'4. $C_9H_{10}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 18'54 ; S, 31'79 per cent).

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